

Protocol Lab 2
Digital Preservation
188.475 – SS18

Name	Matrnr.
Alexander Rashed	01325897
Georg Haggmann	01226641

Contents

1	Introduction	3
2	Installation	3
2.1	Available Options	3
2.2	Process	4
2.3	Quality of Documentation	4
3	Content Organization	5
3.1	Supported content types	5
3.2	Collections	5
3.3	Versioning and Identifiers	5
4	Metadata	6
5	Content presentation	6
5.1	CKAN	6
5.2	DSpace	8
6	Content Search and Discovery	8
7	User Management and access rights	10
7.1	Roles	10
7.2	Embargo	11
7.3	Authentication	11
7.4	Privacy and Security	11
8	Reporting and administration	12
8.1	CKAN	12
9	Interoperability	14
9.1	APIs	14
9.2	Data migration	14
10	Tool	15
11	Conclusion	17

1 Introduction

In this report we will describe and compare two open source repository systems, CKAN and DSpace. CKAN originated from Open Knowledge International, a British NGO. DSpace started as a cooperation between developers from MIT and HP labs. Both have important users and belong to the biggest repository systems.

2 Installation

2.1 Available Options

2.1.1 CKAN

For CKAN, three official ways of installation are available. These options are described in detail in the documentation of CKAN¹. The first is the installation from an operating system package, i.e. a deb file. The second option is to install the program directly from the source. The third is running CKAN from a docker-compose file available in the GitHub-Repository.

All of these methods have various advantages and disadvantages. Installing from a package is rather fast and easy, but requires specific versions of an operating system. An installation from source is the most effort, but runs on most operating systems. The third option, running CKAN as a collection of docker containers, is a trade-off between the flexibility of a source install and the ease of installation of the package install. For greater comparability between systems (to eliminate the influence of the different setups, OSes, environments, etc. of the team members as far as possible) and the greater ease of installation we decided to use the docker-compose-method.

2.1.2 DSpace

For DSpace, only two official options were available. The first is the normal installation of the program from the source files, outlined in the official documentation². The second option is the official Vagrant-Box from the DSpace-GitHub-Repository³. We decided on the Vagrant-Box, again for greater comparability between different systems and for greater ease of installation.

¹<http://docs.ckan.org/en/latest/maintaining/installing/index.html>

²<https://wiki.duraspace.org/display/DSDOC6x/Installing+DSpace>

³<https://wiki.duraspace.org/display/DSDOC6x/Installing+DSpace>

2.2 Process

2.2.1 CKAN

For the process of installing CKAN, we followed the guide in the documentation⁴. This was a bit lengthier than the installation process of DSpace. A lot of the actions needed to install CKAN were manual, e.g. setting requirements, creating admin users, etc.. We mainly used the standard environment outlined in the .env.template-File, the only addition that was necessary was setting a higher file size limit to process the videos used in our sample migration (since 10 MB is the default size limit of resources, which is not enough for most videos). Although manual, the installation process was very straightforward with no unforeseen problems.

2.2.2 DSpace

The installation of DSpace as a vagrant box should happen automatically, i.e. cloning the Git-Repository, starting up vagrant and waiting for the box to configure itself. De facto it needed a lot of installation/configuring the environment for the box to properly start itself up. As soon as this configuration is done, however, starting a new box is very easy. Steps that were taken to ensure a functioning vagrant startup were:

- Installing vagrant plugins, not all marked as mandatory (vagrant-disksize, vagrant-vbguest)
- Adding the same SSH-Key to the SSH-Agent running on the machine and a usable GitHub-Account
- Changing the Box to another link provided in a DSpace-Support forum

After the startup, to enable the REST-API without configuring an SSL-Server, the mandatory HTTPS-usage had to be turned off.

2.3 Quality of Documentation

The documentation for source installation is very good for both projects. The documentation of CKAN for the Docker-Installation was also very high quality. For the DSpace-Vagrant box, the documentation withholds several points that are necessary to get a functioning box. Help with problems is available for both systems. The DSpace-Vagrant box is mainly intended for developers on the DSpace-Project to quickly get a developing environment and not for regular use, which can be one explanation for the missing documentation.

⁴<http://docs.ckan.org/en/latest/maintaining/installing/install-from-docker-compose.html>

3 Content Organization

3.1 Supported content types

Both CKAN and DSpace are able to save and preserve a wide variety of files. DSpace claims that it can store any file type.⁵ Not all file types are supported at an equal level though. In CKAN, the built-in file viewer allows the user to display files in various ways.⁶ Here, every format needs its own plugin. For nearly all common data types used in repositories (CSV, XML, Excel, images, etc.), there are plugins ready. The situation in DSpace is very similar, with both external and internal file previewers to choose from.⁷ For both systems, new viewers for file formats can be defined and implemented.

3.2 Collections

Both repository systems support collections, although they are defined differently and have slightly different use cases. CKAN has its datasets linked to organizations, so normally every dataset is linked to a specific organization. It is however possible to turn off this mandatory linkage and allow datasets which are not owned by an organization.⁸ Groups, however, are used as an optional way of grouping together different datasets, e.g. all datasets of a project or a theme. In DSpace, it is mandatory for datasets to belong to a given collection, that is itself part of one or more communities.

3.3 Versioning and Identifiers

CKAN documentation does not give much information about any identifiers that are used, but it uses UUIDs that are not persistent to identify datasets, organizations, etc.. There are however extensions and plugins available that assign persistent identifiers to resources. DSpace uses CNRI handles to uniquely and persistently identify datasets.⁹, a proprietary registry handled by the Corporation for National Research Initiatives.

Versioning in CKAN works by using the Versioned Domain Model. Other answers in the CKAN-GitHub-Repo indicate that versioning should be possible, but has been neglected for quite some time and that it is hard to actually get older versions of datasets.¹⁰ There are plans to migrate from vdm to SQLAlchemy, but as of now nothing definite has happened.¹¹

⁵<http://www.duraspace.org/dspace/resources/technical-specifications/>

⁶docs.ckan.org/en/latest/maintaining/data-viewer.html

⁷<https://wiki.duraspace.org/display/DSPACE/Document+Viewer+Integration>

⁸<http://docs.ckan.org/en/ckan-2.7.3/user-guide.html#datasets-and-resources>

⁹<https://wiki.duraspace.org/display/DSDOC5x/Functional+Overview#FunctionalOverview-PersistentURLsandIdentifiers>

¹⁰<https://github.com/ckan/ckan/issues/1863>

¹¹<https://github.com/ckan/ideas-and-roadmap/issues/41>

Versioning in DSpace is better implemented and has much better visibility than in CKAN. Viewing the file history of a file is easily possible once Item Level Versioning is activated.¹² The documentation seems to be not quite up to date in this case though, so it is not clear if e.g. "Identified Challenges & Known Issues in DSpace 4.0" are still relevant for the current DSpace 6.0 version.

4 Metadata

CKAN uses mainly its own CKAN Attributes standard. Here, three concepts are defined to describe a given data set:¹³

- *package*: title, notes, tags, revision_timestamp, owner_org, maintainer, maintainer_email
- *resource*: description format, resource_type, webstore_url, size, group (name, title, type, state, etc)
- *organization*: name, id, title, description, state

It is possible to define an unlimited number of additional (extra-)fields for any given dataset. It is also possible to extend the metadata schema through plugins, although in our test we did not manage to make this feature work. Even if it worked like it is described in the documentation¹⁴, it is very hard and time consuming to even add single fields. Implementing a whole metadata standard like DCTERMS would take a long time.

DSpace on the other hand uses a variety of widely recognized metadata standards. It has built in support for the Default Dublin Core Metadata Registry (DC), the Dublin Core Terms Registry (DCTERMS) and the Default Bitstream Format Registry.¹⁵ Additionally, it is very easy to define other metadata standards in the UI of the program or over the API with minimal overhead.

5 Content presentation

5.1 CKAN

In CKAN, datasets are presented with the name, a description and the metadata of the dataset. Figure 1 shows such a dataset.

¹²<https://wiki.duraspace.org/display/DSDOC6x/Item+Level+Versioning>

¹³<http://knowhow.opendatamonitor.eu/odresearch/metadata-standards/>

¹⁴<http://docs.ckan.org/en/ckan-2.7.3/extensions/adding-custom-fields.html>

¹⁵<https://wiki.duraspace.org/display/DSDOC4x/Metadata+and+Bitstream+Format+Registries#MetadataandBitstreamFormatRegistries-DefaultBitstreamFormatRegistry>

Document Sample 1

Document Sample for DPUE 1, containing the Exercise PDF of Task 2

Data and Resources

Additional Info

Field	Value
Author	Georg Hagmann
Maintainer	Georg Hagmann
Version	1.0
State	active
Last Updated	June 4, 2018, 11:59 AM (UTC+02:00)
Created	June 4, 2018, 11:59 AM (UTC+02:00)

Figure 1: Picture of a dataset in CKAN

Resources follow a similar schema with resource-specific metadata. Additionally, there are plugins available for different filetypes to display and preview files without having to open them. There are standard plugins for Pictures, Text and Data fields plus there are additional plugins available for other filetypes (PDF, etc.). If no such viewer is available, the data must be downloaded to be viewed.

Figure 2: Preview of a PNG-File in CKAN

5.2 DSpace

DSpace does not provide previews out of the box. For some files, the browser can be used to display files without having to download them (e.g. PDF-Files in most modern Browsers), but DSpace itself does not provide any methods to do it. It is possible to implement previews and there is a list of possible online viewers¹⁶, but no ready made plugins. The datasets and the metadata are presented in a similar way to CKAN with a short description and some metadata. A click on "Show full item record" shows additional metadata information for a file.

Figure 3: Picture of a dataset in DSpace, XMLUI

A peculiarity of DSpace is that it has two built in User Interfaces, one available at `dspace-url/xmlui`, one at `dspace-url/jspui`. The information and functionality is similar, but the presentation is different. The metadata of the dataset presented in Figure 3 is from the XML-UI, in the JSP-UI the same information is presented as shown in Figure 5

6 Content Search and Discovery

In CKAN it is possible to search for every standard metadata entry. It is possible to browse through the datasets of organizations, groups, etc.. Faceted search is enabled by default. It is also possible to define tags for datasets to group them for easier browsing. Fulltext search is not enabled by default, but again there are plugins available for this.¹⁷

In DSpace, it is also possible to search for every metadata entry. Every search is a full text search, i.e. searching for a string outputs all datasets where this string appears in

¹⁶<https://wiki.duraspace.org/display/DSPACE/Document+Viewer+Integration>

¹⁷<https://github.com/transparenzportalhamburg/ckanext-fulltext>

[Show simple item record](#)

dc.rights.license	Creative Commons Attribution, http://www.opendefinition.org/licenses/cc-by
dc.contributor.author	Georg Hagmann, georg.hagmann@tuwien.ac.at
dc.date.accessioned	2018-06-04T09:25:58Z
dc.date.available	2018-06-04T09:25:58Z
dc.identifier.uri	http://localhost:8080/xmlui/handle/123456789/14
dc.description.abstract	Video Sample for DPUE 2
dc.title	Video Sample 1
dc.description.version	1.0
audiovisual.Bitrate.Bitrate	541
audiovisual.Length.Length	10

Files in this item

Name: video_2017-07-04_... [View/Open](#)
Size: 722.8Kb
Format: Unknown

This item appears in the following Collection(s)

- [843803b6-ce0a-431e-a536-0366ca76a1fa](#)
[Show simple item record](#)

Figure 4: Picture of extended metadata of an item in DSpace

[My DSpace Site](#) / [organization-for-tests](#) / [843803b6-ce0a-431e-a536-0366ca76a1fa](#)

Please use this identifier to cite or link to this item: <http://localhost:8080/xmlui/handle/123456789/14>

Title:	Video Sample 1
Authors:	Georg Hagmann, georg.hagmann@tuwien.ac.at
Abstract:	Video Sample for DPUE 2
URI:	http://localhost:8080/xmlui/handle/123456789/14
Appears in Collections:	843803b6-ce0a-431e-a536-0366ca76a1fa

Files in This Item:

File	Size	Format	
video_2017-07-04_21-19-20.mp4	722.83 kB	Unknown	View/Open

[Show full item record](#)

Figure 5: Picture of a dataset in DSpace, JSPUI

the metadata. Faceted search is also possible and enabled by default. Fulltextsearch is available by default, but limited to some specific files like Word or Plaintext-files.¹⁸

¹⁸<https://duraspace.zendesk.com/hc/en-us/articles/200436516-Does-DSpaceDirect-provide-full-text-search>

Figure 6: Faceted search in CKAN

Figure 7: Faceted search in DSpace

7 User Management and access rights

7.1 Roles

In CKAN it is possible to set permissions for every package, group and organization. Users can be assigned different roles (Editor, Admin, etc.) that enable the user to interact with

an object in a specific way. Users can also be grouped in authorization groups to set privileges not only for one object, but for a group of objects. Additional roles can be added if the basic roles do not suffice.

In DSpace, every user gets assigned an E-Person. This E-Person can be added to various groups, thus getting privileges linked with the membership of the group (e.g. editing files of the group). This groups can be edited and added to provide access-control of datasets.

7.2 Embargo

In CKAN, there is currently no function available for setting embargoes, although one is in discussion.¹⁹

DSpace has a sophisticated built in embargo function that enables users to set embargoes for specific dates on specific datasets and more. It is also capable of setting embargoes via given metadata.²⁰

7.3 Authentication

CKAN uses a normal Email+Password-Authentication out of the box. Registered users also have a personal API-Key for their account, used to register to the API. There is a wide variety of plugins available for different authentication mechanisms, e.g. a plugin providing LDAP-authentication for a CKAN-server.²¹

DSpace has a wider variety of possible authentication methods built in. Out of the box, authentication via password, Shibboleth, LDAP, IP and X.509 Certificate are possible. The API uses the standard authentication method of the server, e.g. if password authentication is the standard method of authentication, it is necessary to send username and password to the server to receive an ID-Token used in further interactions with the server.

7.4 Privacy and Security

7.4.1 CKAN

The standard security practices of CKAN are quite weak. No brute-force protection is implemented, automatic logouts after inactivity do not happen, etc., CSRF is in some places possible. For servers where more security is necessary, plugins are available that remedy these issues.²²

¹⁹<https://github.com/ckan/ideas-and-roadmap/issues/51>

²⁰<https://wiki.duraspace.org/display/DSDOC6x/Embargo>

²¹<http://extensions.ckan.org/extension/ldap/>

²²<https://github.com/data-govt-nz/ckanext-security>

We could not find much about CKANs privacy standards, but the current very open data (e.g. it is possible to get a list of all users without sysadmin access)²³ suggest that it is rather open.

7.4.2 DSpace

DSpace is a bit more focused on security out of the box. It is configured to use HTTPS only for the REST-API out of the box, a feature we had to manually disable to be able to use the API without first configuring a TLS-Server. It also has documentation focused on securing the DSpace-Instance.²⁴

For privacy, DSpace has current documentation, focusing on the impact of the DSGVO, although not every section is already filled (the "Proposals of Change" are still empty).²⁵

8 Reporting and administration

8.1 CKAN

CKAN has a sysadmin-page, this page though can only be used to purge (i.e. not only making datasets invisible, but actually delete them from disk) datasets and configuring the main page. All other activities, e.g. managing datasets, adding plugins, extending Metadata, etc. have to be done either on dedicated pages or in code. Many changes can only be achieved through plugins, which themselves need various changes to different files (e.g. to generate a new metadata schema, changes have to happen in at least five files). CKAN doesn't provide many statistics on the website if not configured to do so, e.g. by installing one of the dedicated plugins for statistics.²⁶ It has a built in support for page view tracking that is not enabled by default.²⁷

²³<https://github.com/ckan/ckan/issues/3441>

²⁴<https://wiki.duraspace.org/display/DSPACE/SecuringDspace>

²⁵<https://wiki.duraspace.org/display/DSPACE/Data+Protection+and+Privacy>

²⁶<http://docs.ckan.org/en/ckan-2.7.3/maintaining/stats.html>

²⁷<http://docs.ckan.org/en/ckan-2.7.3/maintaining/tracking.html#tracking>

Figure 8: Admin Panel in CKAN

DSpace however, has a more extensive sysadmin page. Here it is possible to directly manipulate metadata standards, defaults, access control and various other settings. DSpace offers some methods to gather statistics. DSpace Google Analytics can be used to record user interface traffic. SOLR has statistics about individual items, collections and more. As an example, the SOLR statistics on an dataset home page record:²⁸

- Total visits of the item
- Total visits for the bitstreams attached to the item
- Visits of the item over a timespan of the last 7 months
- Top 10 country views from where the visits originate
- Top 10 cities from where the visits originate

Figure 9: Admin Panel in DSpace

²⁸<https://wiki.duraspace.org/display/DSDOC6x/SOLR+Statistics#SOLRStatistics-PageviewandDownloadstatistics>

9 Interoperability

There is no standard interoperability between the two repositories meaning a single export functionality in CKAN dumping the data to a format which can be imported into DSpace.

There is a project which provides a runtime integration from DSpace to CKAN²⁹ in the form of a DSpace-CRIS compatible plugin. The aim of this plugin however is to use the best features of both repositories (like CKAN's data preview features), not to migrate from one to another.

Therefore when it comes to migrating the data in CKAN to DSpace one has to use the facilitated HTTP APIs to export the data from one repository, transform the meta-data from one nomenclature / domain to the other and insert the data into the second repository.

9.1 APIs

The CKAN API³⁰ is not very RESTful (meaning the architectural style, lots of method URIs, no proper usage of HTTP methods etc.), but at least it's consistent in the usage. For CKAN the official python package *ckanapi*³¹ is provided (and was used in our migration script). All major entities are covered by the API, especially it is possible to export *organizations*, *groups*, *packages* and their *resources*.

The DSpace API³² is more RESTful (every entity is a resource with its own URI, proper usage of HTTP methods etc.) but the documentation itself is minimalistic (meaning nearly non-existent). Unfortunately no official (or up-to-date unofficial) package, neither for python nor for any other language, is available. The API does allow the import of *communities* (a CKAN *organization*), *collections* (somewhat like a CKAN *group*), *items* (a CKAN *package*) and *bitstreams* (a CKAN *resource*).

9.2 Data migration

The data migration is working as expected, but during the implementation of the migration script we were facing several problems:

- The DSpace API is nearly not documented at all. For the creation of bitstreams the API is even misleading.
- The nomenclature in the different repositories is completely different, which is a bit confusing.

²⁹<https://github.com/4Science/dspace-ckan>

³⁰<http://docs.ckan.org/en/ckan-2.7.3/api/>

³¹<https://github.com/ckan/ckanapi>

³²<https://wiki.duraspace.org/display/DSDOC6x/REST+API>

- The relations between the entities in the two repositories are not the same. DSpace *items* always have to be in a *collection*. CKAN *packages* however can be stored directly in the space of an *organization*. Therefore we had to create a default DSpace *collection* for each DSpace *community* where the corresponding CKAN *organization* contains CKAN *packages* which are not part of a CKAN *group*.
- The DSpace API does not even mention how to provide metadata for an entity.
- In order to use the DSpace REST API we had to manually disable the *security-Constraint* in the *web.xml* of the web application and perform a complete rebuild / redeployment within the vagrant image.

9.2.1 Export limitations

In CKAN, additional metadata is stored as *extras*. These extras can be on every level and do not have to follow specific schemas. Therefore we weren't able to export the schema from CKAN dynamically. Our migration script is now creating the schema (hardcoded in the script) if it doesn't exist yet.

The CKAN resource formats cannot be exported using the API, therefore we couldn't include them into the migration.

9.2.2 Lost information

During the migration, the CKAN resource formats are lost. Besides that all information is migrated, but some information is transformed during the migration (f.e. licenses are simple metadata entries in DSpace and full fledged entities in CKAN, they have to be flattened).

10 Tool

The tool we have developed to migrate from CKAN to DSpace and list data from both repositories is hosted on GitHub³³.

The output of the command "lckan" (meaning list ckan) with the sample datasets in the GitHub Repository can be seen in Figure 10.

The output of the command "ldspace" (meaning list dspace) with the sample datasets in the GitHub Repository can be seen in Figure 11.

The third and last possible command is the "migrate" command, which automatically migrates all available data from the CKAN- to the DSpace-Repository. The output of such a program can be found in Figure 12.

³³<https://github.com/alexrashed/tu-dpue-lab2-ss18>

```
alex@alex-notebook:~/Repos/tu-dpue-lab2-ss18$ ./script.py lckan
audio-sample-1
audio-sample-2
coding-sample-1
coding-sample-2
data-sample-2-csv
data-sample-csv
document-sample-1
document-sample-2
license-selector-screenshot
students-graphic
video-sample-1
video-sample-2
alex@alex-notebook:~/Repos/tu-dpue-lab2-ss18$
```

Figure 10: Output of lckan

```
alex@alex-notebook:~/Repos/tu-dpue-lab2-ss18$ ./script.py ldspace
Audio Sample 1
Audio Sample 2
Coding Sample 1
Coding Sample 2
Data Sample 2 CSV
Data Sample CSV
Document Sample 1
Document Sample 2
License Selector Screenshot
Students Graphic
Video Sample 1
Video Sample 2
alex@alex-notebook:~/Repos/tu-dpue-lab2-ss18$
```

Figure 11: Output of ldspace

Problems with the migration have already been discussed. All three commands have been realized by communicating with the APIs of the respective repository. More information and sample data can be found in the Readme of the Github repository.

```

alex@alex-notebook:~/Repos/tu-dpue-lab2-ss18$ ./script.py migrate > output/migrate.log
alex@alex-notebook:~/Repos/tu-dpue-lab2-ss18$ cat output/migrate
cat: output/migrate: No such file or directory
alex@alex-notebook:~/Repos/tu-dpue-lab2-ss18$ cat output/migrate.log
Creating DSpace community for CKAN organization: organization-for-tests
Created DSpace community with UUID b1fdb67-0a0c-445a-ae5b-eaae1de3c316
Creating DSpace collection for community with ID b1fdb67-0a0c-445a-ae5b-eaae1de3c316: {'name':
'33e875a2-5557-49de-b927-9271af66ce7a'}
Created DSpace collection with UUID 22cd32e5-fc22-4eba-aceb-51da1e30328d
{'key': 'Bitrate', 'value': '19.7'}
{'key': 'Length', 'value': '6'}
Creating DSpace item {"name": "audio-sample-1", "metadata": [{"key": "dc.title", "value": "Audio
Sample 1"}, {"key": "dc.rights.license", "value": "Creative Commons Attribution, http://www.ope
ndefinition.org/licenses/cc-by"}, {"key": "dc.contributor.author", "value": "Georg Hagmann, geor
g.hagmann@tuwien.ac.at"}, {"key": "dc.description.version", "value": "1.0"}, {"key": "dc.descrip
tion.abstract", "value": "Audio Sample for DPUE 2"}, {"key": "audiovisual.Bitrate.Bitrate", "val
ue": "19.7"}, {"key": "audiovisual.Length.Length", "value": "6"}]} in collection with ID 22cd32e
5-fc22-4eba-aceb-51da1e30328d
Created DSpace item with ID 90ad433f-917b-4a5c-9e7b-b922fd1a1a42
Creating DSpace bitstream {"name": "audio_2018-05-21_13-58-10.ogg", "mimeType": "audio/ogg", "me
tadata": [{"key": "dc.title", "value": "audio_2018-05-21_13-58-10.ogg"}, {"key": "dc.format", "v
alue": "audio/ogg"}, {"key": "dc.format.mimeType", "value": "audio/ogg"}, {"key": "dc.descriptio
n", "value": "Audio File Recorded for DPUE Task 2."}]} for item with ID 90ad433f-917b-4a5c-9e7b-
b922fd1a1a42
Created DSpace bitstream with ID 86a6f5e6-72e7-4a8c-bbc2-101e0074c1fa
Created DSpace bitstream data for bitstream with ID 86a6f5e6-72e7-4a8c-bbc2-101e0074c1fa
{'key': 'Bitrate', 'value': '20'}
{'key': 'Length', 'value': '5'}

```

Figure 12: Output of migrate

11 Conclusion

Both repository systems have relatively clear upsides and downsides. CKAN feels like the more mature system with a larger community and a lot of available plugins. The documentation of CKAN is in most regards superior to the documentation of DSpace and the setup is less complicated. On the other hand, DSpace has a lot of interesting features that are still not supported in CKAN (e.g. Embargoes). Many features of DSpace, especially the API, feel very well implemented, but suffer very much from the lack of good documentation. In CKAN, however, it is very hard to actually change many settings and needed things. Implementing a new metadata standard proved to be very hard in CKAN, whereas in DSpace, it was a matter of minutes. DSpace feels more flexible in many regards than CKAN, where actual changes to usage/workflow are very hard. It feels like a decision between these systems can't be felled for every instance, but very much depends on the circumstances of usage. If the additional flexibility of DSpace is needed or helpful for a project, it is a clear winner. If very few changes to the CKAN-standard are needed, the better documentation and easier setup of CKAN wins.